

An analysis of Rural Education infrastructure in India

Dr. Lalit Kumar Goyal

Assistant professor- Department of sociology, Pt. Mahadev shukla krishak p.g. college Gaur Basti, India

Author Email: l.kgoyal78@gmail.com

Abstract —The greater proportion of people in the world live in rural areas. Around 68% of Indian population are belongs to rural environment. Though the contribution of rural areas to the national economic development is limited, however specially in developing countries a huge amount of economic contribution depends on rural areas. Therefore, rural development is key for the overall economic development of many developing countries including India. Rural development is an eminent factor for the development of our economy. The crucial motivating factor for the development of the economy in today's time is education. Like in the body of human being liver is responsible for the proper functioning of the body, in the same way education acts a backbone for the economy. To explore this significant role of education in India especially in rural India, this paper tries to explain the present condition of rural education, rural education v/s urban education failures and problems being faced by the rural education. It also focused the various initiatives been taken by the government and some of the suggestions for improving the education system in rural or remote areas.

Keywords: Education, Rural Education, Scenario, Problems, Suggestions

I. INTRODUCTION

The contribution of rural India towards the economic development is not hidden from any of us. Earlier the people used to correlate rural development with agricultural development and thus focus was only on the increased agricultural production. But with the changing time, this misbelieve has also changed. Today the concept of rural development is fundamentally different that it was used to be 2 or 3 decades ago. Now rural development includes development improving the quality of life of rural people. It constitutes improvement in their health and nutrition, education, safe and healthy environment, fairness in income distribution and no discrimination in gender.

Quality and access to education is the major concern in rural schools as there are fewer committed teachers, lack of proper text books and learning materials in the schools. Though government schools exist, but when compared to private schools then quality is major issue. Majority of people living in villages have understood the importance of education and know that it is the only way to get rid of poverty. But due to lack of money they are not able to send their children to private schools and hence depend upon government schools for education. Above that in some government schools there is only one teacher for the entire school. Every village is not provided with school which means that students have to go to another village to get education. Owing to this parents usually do not send their children to school, leading to a failure in achieving rural education in India.

The development of a country primarily depends on the education system of that country. Therefore, to achieve continuous development of the country, all the branches of education system should be improved. As it is known that more than half of the population of India belongs to the rural area, therefore the education system in rural area also plays an important contribution in the development of the country. Education plays an important role on the development of the rural individual, family, community, and society, which leads to reduced poverty, and controlled unemployment. Education has a major role in rural systems of supply, production, marketing, health care, education, personnel maintenance and governance which ultimately leads to the rural development. Education also plays an important role in imparting social change, improving socio-economic status of people and standard of living, providing trained manpower in rural areas, linking rural and urban sector, and providing employment and income opportunities to the rural people. Keeping in view the importance of education in rural areas the Government of India has launched many programs to improve the education system of rural India, but still there is a huge gap exists between the urban and rural education system.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study are as follows-

- To study about the present scenario of rural education in India.

- To study about problems faced in rural education in India.
- To provide some suggestive measures to improve the rural education in India.

III. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present study is mainly based on secondary data which has been collected from the various documents, reports, journals, internet and other sources.

IV. RECENT SCENARIO OF INDIA'S EDUCATION SECTOR: AT A GLANCE

Recently, the 17th Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) 2022 was released by NGO Pratham.

What is ASER?

- The ASER, is an annual, citizen-led household survey that aims to understand whether children in rural India are enrolled in school and whether they are learning.
- ASER has been conducted every year since 2005 in all rural districts of India. It is the largest citizen-led survey in India.
- ASER surveys provided representative estimates of the enrolment status of children aged 3-16 and the basic reading and arithmetic levels of children aged 5-16 at the national, state and district level.

What are the Findings of the Report?

- Enrollment in Government Schools:
 - According to the ASER, 2022 the country has seen an increase in the enrollment of children in government schools.
- Basic Reading and Arithmetic Skills:
 - There has been a decline in the basic reading and arithmetic skills of young children in Class 3 and Class 5 in India.
- Proportion of Girls not Enrolled:
 - The decrease in the proportion of girls not enrolled in schools for the age group 11-14 from 4.1% in 2018 to 2% in 2022 is a significant improvement and a positive development.
 - This indicates that efforts to promote gender equality in education have been effective and have helped to increase the enrollment of girls in schools.

Parameters	2018	2022	Trend
Overall Enrollment (Age Group 6-14)	97.2%	98.4%	Positive
Enrolled in Government School (Age Group 6-14)	65.6%	72.9%	Positive
Girls not Enrolled in School (Age Group 11-14)	4.1%	2%	Positive
Children in Std I-VIII Taking Paid Private Tuition Classes	26.4%	30.5%	Positive
Children in Std III who are able to at least do subtraction	28.2%	25.9%	Negative

Children in Std V across India who can do division	27.9%	25.6%	Negative
Government Schools with Less than 60 Students Enrolled	29.4%	29.9%	Negative
Average Teacher Attendance	85.4%	87.1%	Positive
Fraction of Schools with Useable Girls' Toilets	66.4%	68.4%	Positive
Schools with Drinking Water Availability	74.8%	76%	Positive

(Source: Annual Status of Education Report (ASER)-2022)

IV.I. PROBLEMS FACED IN RURAL EDUCATION IN INDIA

IV.I.I. FINANCIAL ISSUES

- To begin with, low incomes make education a secondary priority.
- Education is often viewed as a cost instead of investment by rural people. They would prefer the kids to work hard and earn money.
- Whenever it concerns higher education, the dearth of suitable colleges nearby forces students to consider relocating to cities, which increases their costs. As a result, enrolment rates are low, while dropout rates are greater.

IV.I.II. LACK OF FACULTY AND INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITIES

- Children seem to have little access to fundamental learning resources like well-equipped and infrastructurally good classrooms, computers, laboratories, and playgrounds, to name a few.
- Teachers are frequently unqualified or fail to appear, resulting in low educational quality. Students' motivation to join or attend school suffers as a result of this.

IV.I.III. LACK OF PROPER GUIDANCE

- Students from remote regions have enormous potential and thus are willing to learn, but they lack the proper coaching due to the poor rural education scenario. This is necessary for the kids, as well as for the guardians.

IV.I.IV. GENDER INEQUALITY

- One of the major issues in rural education that still persists is gender inequality and lack of girl child education.
- Women are not permitted to attend school in certain areas. Or, if permitted, it is restricted to a specified age range. They are not permitted to leave their community in pursuit of higher education and better employment opportunities.

IV.I.V. DIGITAL DIVIDEND

- Rural communities, unlike metropolitan ones, lack access to advanced learning resources.
- The emergence of digital platforms and tools, for instance, is the most recent educational instrument.
- Unfortunately, these sophisticated learning aids are not available in rural locations. Rural communities face issues such as poor internet connectivity, digital gadgets, and efficient or uninterrupted supply of power.

IV.II. SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING RURAL EDUCATION IN INDIA

Some of the suggestions that can be adopted for improving the education system in rural:

- The curriculum of rural education can be updated and should accompany education related to farming, gardening etc.
- To attract more number of students and creating enthusiasm in them for learning, visual aids like projectors, television etc. can be used to show some educational movies.
- To motivate the teachers they should be made to feel proud that by teaching in the rural or remote area they are acting as a helping hand in the development of economy.
- Some special sessions or classes can be conducted for the parents to make them realize the significance of education for their children.
- To appreciate the efforts of students, some type of scholarships either in the form of gifts or books can be given to them who perform well in the class.

IV.II.I. INITIATIVES TAKEN BY THE GOVERNMENT

For promoting the importance of education in India, Ministry of Law and Justice had introduced 'The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009'. It is an

Act introduced to provide free and compulsory education to all children between the ages of six to fourteen years. Several central and state level initiatives have been in operation from the early 1980s. The main objectives of all these initiatives include increasing girls enrolment, improving educational outcomes, strengthening community involvement, improving teaching and learning materials, and providing in-service teacher training in villages. Some of these initiatives are:

IV.II.II. NON-FORMAL EDUCATION SCHEME

The Non-Formal Education (NFE) was introduced in 1979-80 by the central government to support the formal system in providing education to all children below the age of 14 years. This scheme was focused especially in the educationally backward districts of Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal from 1987-88.

The scheme was introduced because the National Policy on Education (NPE) had recognized that the formal schooling system could not reach all children. Therefore, a large and systematic programme of non-formal education would be required to educate the school dropouts, and children from habitations, where no schools are present, working children and girls, who could not attend whole day schools.

IV.II.III. SARVA SIKSHA ABHIYAN (SSA)

The main goal of this program is that all children of 6-11 years of age should complete primary education by the year 2007 and all children of 6-14 years of age should complete

eight years of schooling by 2010. This plan covers the whole country with special emphasis on girl education and education of Schedule Caste (SC) and Schedule Tribe (ST) children and

children with special needs. The SSA centers are mainly opened in those areas, which do not have any school or where schools are very far off. Special girl oriented programs include: Girl education at elementary level, National Program for Education of Girls at Elementary Level (NPEGEL), Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV), Mahila Samakhya Scheme.

IV.II.IV. DISTRICT PRIMARY EDUCATION PROGRAM

District Primary Education Programme (DPEP) was launched in November 1994. This programme was launched to operationalize the strategies to achieve Universal Elementary Education at the particular district level, rather than imposing the same rule, i.e., educational programmes were decentralized through this scheme. It emphasizes on decentralized management, community mobilization, and district-specific planning based on contextual and research-based inputs available to each district.

IV.II.V. NATIONAL PROGRAMME OF NUTRITIONAL SUPPORT TO PRIMARY EDUCATION (SCHOOL MEAL PROGRAMME)

This programme was launched on 15th August 1995 with a view to increase enrolment, retention and attendance in primary schools by augmenting nutritional meal to children.

Under this scheme children attending the school are given free cooked meal of 100gms every day and positive results have gained with this scheme. By 1997-98 this scheme has covered around 110million children of primary school. It is implemented for the students of classes' I-V.

IV.II.VI. OPERATION BLACKBOARD

The scheme of Operation Blackboard was launched in 1987 in pursuance of National Policy of Education—Programme of Action, to provide minimum essential facilities to all primary schools in the country. This is a large operation and was launched after the external evaluation of the scheme had indicated that lack of training of teachers in using the teaching material, and lack of uniform facilities, which are provided without modification, according to local needs were found to be some of the drawbacks of implementation of the scheme.

CONCLUSION

Rural India faces challenges in acquiring education due to a shortage of institutions and facilities, a scarcity of instructors, religious and cultural traditions, a significant distance between home and school, and a general lack of understanding of the need for education.

The development of schools in rural areas, the provision of suitable infrastructure as well as other resources, the use of contemporary technology in education, and the creation of awareness regarding the value of education are all ways to improve the current state of rural education.

REFERENCES

1. Carnoy, M. and Samioff, J. (1990). Education and Social Transition in the Third World (Princeton University Press, 1990).
2. Cremin, Lawrence (1976). Toward an Ecology of Education (Excerpt from Public Education, John Dewey Society, Pub:USIS, New Delhi, 1976).
3. Dharampal (1983). The Beautiful Tree : Indigenous Indian Education in the Eighteenth Century (Biblia Impex, Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi,1983).
4. Di, Bona (1983). One Teacher, One School : Adam's Reports (Biblia Impex, Pvt. Ltd. 1983).
5. Gandhi, M.K. (1995) India of my Dreams (Navajivan Publishing House, 1995).
6. Iyer, R.N. (1995). The Essential Writings of Mahatma Gandhi (OUP,1995).
7. Joshi, P.C. (1992). Cultural Communication and Social Change (Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi, 1992).
8. Naik, J.P. and Nurullah, S. (1975). A Students' History of Education in India (McMillan & Co., Bombay, 1975).